

REBELLION OF INMATES AS THE EFFECT OF UNFILLED BASIC RIGHTS

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Abstact

In recent years, there have been many jail escapes and riots. The most audacious case happened in May 2017 in Pekanbaru State Jail Class IIB where there were 448 prisoners who escaped. The number of prisoners in Pekanbaru State Jail Class IIB amounts to 1,870 people. This figure shows that there is an overcapacity issue for a jail class IIB. The research problem in this study focuses on the fulfillment of prisoners' basic rights and jail escapes as an effect of failing to meet those rights. This study aims to find out and describe the fulfillment of prisoners' basic rights in Pekanbaru Jail Class IIB. This research was conducted in the Pekanbaru Jail Class IIB by using qualitative approach in July 2017. Data was collected by using observation, interview and document studies techniques, which was then processed and analyzed qualitatively. The result of this study indicates that, what triggers prison escapes are overcapacity issue and unmet prisoners' rights in the form of basic needs. Basic necessities of life such as clean water, decent food, room ventilation, and bed for sleeping are not sufficiently fulfilled. In addition, a 4x3-meter room in Pekanbaru jail is inhabited by 30 people even though it should only be inhabited by 8 people. This study provides a number of suggestions, one of which includes the need to increase the role of government in managing overcrowded jail and that the government must bear the responsibility to fulfill of the prisoners' rights.

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1.Introduction

State prisons (or correctional institutions) and jails are technical implementation units (Unit Pelaksana Teknis/UPT) that carry out the duties and functions of dealing with prisoners and conducting rehabilitation service for them. Correctional services have such a hard task, in which it has to be able to restore the relationship of life, life and livelihood. A very crucial issue in correctional facilities nowadays is related to a big number of overcrowded state prisons and jails existing. This issue affects jail officers in carrying out their duties and functions. One of the few things they must overcome is that they have to keep these state prisons and jails safe no matter what.

Regarding to the data obtained from the Correctional Database System on July 31st, 2018, there were only 4 out of 33 regional offices with correctional implementation units that are not overcrowded. This data left 29 regional offices with overcrowded jails. It shows that this issue has turned out to be a very crucial problem. The overcrowded rate on average state prisons and jails in Indonesia is above 100%. This problem will have an impact on organizational

performance as a whole and cause many problems. One problem that is very likely to occur is jail escapes. With present condition, jail escape or jail break will be much easier to happen.

Regarding to the data obtained by the authors from various sources during December 2017 - May 2018, security issue was among the most common problem found in prisons and jails. A few cases found include :

No	Name of Prisons and Jails	Number of Prisoners Escaping
1	Pekanbaru State Jail Class IIB	260 Prisoners
2	Muaro Padang State Prison Class IIA	1 Prisoner
3	Pekanbaru State Prison Class IIA	2 Prisoners
4	Branch of Labuhan Bilik State Jail	16 Prisoners
5	Manokawari State Jail	14 Prisoners
6	Binjai State Jail	7 Prisoners
7	Wamena State Jail	19 Prisoners
8	Tanjung Raja State Jail Class IIA	1 Prisoner
9	Besi Nusakambangan State Jail Class IIA	2 Prisoners

Source : Online news (data processed by author)

Research Question

As stated in background above, the research question that can be formulated is : How can jail escapes be an effect of prisoners' unmet basic rights?

Research Objectives

The objective of this research is to analyze how jail escapes can be an effect of prisoners' unmet basic rights.

2.Methodology

Methodology refers to specific procedures or techniques used to solve problems as a guidance to gain deeper information of an object observed by collecting, compiling and interpreting data to find, develop and test the truth of a knowledge which results in scientific writing, in which the results can be scientifically proven. This study uses a qualitative approach, in which the theory does not become the main starting point. Data obtained in the field will be fairly compared with theory to build a comprehensively general interpretation. This study uses a qualitative approach. As stated by John W. Creswell, "*Qualitative research is an inquiry of understanding based on the methodology of traditions of inquiry that explore the social or human problem. The researcher build a complex, holistic picture, analyze words, report detached views of informants, and conduct the study in natural settings.*" Qualitative research refers to a process of understanding inquiry based on separate methodological traditions that explore a problem or human. The type of this research is descriptive which is intended to describe a phenomenon by examining it regularly, prioritizing objectivity, and being done carefully. Data collected from literature review by studying various legislative provisions

related to correctional facilities. Primary data is collected through field research by conducting a directly persuasive approach with prisoners in Pekanbaru State Jail Class II. Scientific books related to correctional facilities to support existing data. This research took place in Pekanbaru State Jail Class II.

3.Theoretical Framework

Human Rights in State Constitution

Human rights protection is absolutely given to each individual without having to look at and differentiate their background. The recognition of human rights gained its legitimacy internationally through the ratification of the United Nations' Declaration of Human Rights in December 10th, 1948. As a part of the world community, Indonesia must respect human rights contained in DUHAM (Conclusion of MPR Decree Number XVII/MPR/1998; article c). Therefore, Indonesia has participated in ratifying and adopting various regulations concerning human rights originating from international law.

Basic Rights Protection for Prisoners

Human rights are basic human rights that must be given, even though someone is a prisoner. As stated in *A Human Rights Approach Studies*, "*Detainees / prisoners are also human*". As a human being, they also have human rights, no matter how severe the crimes they have committed. The only human rights of prisoners that can be taken away are physical freedom.

In order to protect the human rights of prisoners, the UN, back in 1955, had formalized a number of minimum rights and treatment that must be given to prisoners/detainees while in prison/jail, in the form of the *Minimum Standard Rules for Treatment of Prisoners* (SMR). The provisions contained in the SMR refer to minimum provisions that are "morally" obliged to be adhered in treating prisoners/detainees.

The treatment of prisoners in the form of coaching is the main task of the correctional system. It has been regulated in the Article 2 and Article 3 of the Correctional Law. Article 2 of the Correctional Law states:

"The correctional system is organized to rehabilitate prisoners in order to be fully human, realize mistakes, improve themselves, and be unwilling to commit criminal acts so that they can be accepted again by the community, actively play a role in national development, and live properly as good dan responsible citizens".

In a broader sense, the correctional system is part of the efforts to protect human rights. As part of the Criminal Justice System, the correctional system refers to an agency that fulfills and protects the rights of suspects, defendants and convicts. The focus of this definition is that the Correctional System can be understood as a treatment system for prisoners who are naturally attached with human rights (Dindin Sudirman, 2007: 29).

The main function of the Correctional System in protecting human rights, as affirmed by Dindin Sudirman (Dindin Sudirman, 2007), states that law enforcement by correctional means is an effort to humanize humans. Correctional facilities are institutions that fulfill and protect the rights of suspects (pre-adjudication stage), defendants (adjudication stage) and convicts (post-adjudication stage). In the post-adjudication stage, technical implementation unit in correctional system that is in charge to protect human rights is prison/correctional institution. The function of prison/correctional institution, which are philosophically different from mere prisons, can be understood as an attempt to avoid the occurrence of an inhumane punishment process. One such

effort is to prevent the occurrence of what-so-called prisonization or the process of learning crime and minimize the suffering while in prison.

Prisoners' rights protected by the Correctional Law is an effort to minimize the possibility of prisonization and stigmatization of the community. As explained previously, it can be stated that the protection of human rights is a key success indicator of the tasks and functions implementation by correctional facilities, especially prisoners' rights. The commitment to change the conditions of prisoners is explicitly confirmed by Article 5 of the Correctional Law. It is stated that the system of correctional counseling is carried out based on the principle as follow; care, equality of treatment and service, education, coaching, respect for human dignity, loss of physical freedom is the only suffering, and guaranteed protection over right to keep in touch with certain families and people. In addition, Article 14 of the Correctional Law stipulates that every prisoner has the following rights:

- a. Perform worship according to their religion or belief
- b. Get physical and spiritual care
- c. Get education and teaching
- d. Get proper health and food services
- e. Convey complaints
- f. Get reading material and follow other mass media broadcasts that are not prohibited
- g. Get wages or premiums for work done
- h. Receive family visits, legal counsel, or certain other people
- i. Get a reduction of punishment time (remission)
- j. Get the chance to assimilate including family leave
- k. Get parole
- l. Get leave before free; and
- m. Obtain other rights in accordance with the applicable laws and regulations

At the stage of the implementation of criminal sentences, human rights are integrated into the prisoners' rights that guarantee and are protected by law as a respect for human dignity. Article 10 of the International Convention on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) affirms that all people who lose their freedom are treated humanely and respectfully. Thus, the prison system must be implemented based on essential principles, such as reform, rehabilitation and social reintegration. Furthermore, underage prisoners must be separated from adults and given appropriate treatment for their legal status.

Regarding to the UN guidelines on Standard Minimum Rules For The Treatment of Prisoner, 31 Juli 1957 (Standard Minimum Rules For The Treatment of Prisoner, July 31, 1957), these include :

1. Register book
2. Separation of categories of prisoners
3. Accommodation facilities that must have ventilation
4. Adequate sanitation facilities
5. Getting water and toilet equipment
6. Decent clothes and bedding
7. Healthy food
8. Right to exercise in the open air
9. Right to get general medical doctor and dentist services
10. Right to be treated fairly according to regulations and right to defend themselves if considered interdisciplinary

11. Not permitted confinement in dark cells and corporal punishment
12. Handcuffs and prison jackets cannot be used by prisoners / prisoners
13. Entitled to know the applicable regulations and official channels to get information and submit complaints
14. Right to communicate with outside world
15. Right to obtain reading material in the form of books that are educational
16. Right to obtain religious services
17. Right to obtain collateral for the storage of valuables
18. Notification of death and sickness from family members

Human Rights Perspective on State

"All Human being are born free and equal in dignity and rights" means that every human being is born independent (free) and has the same rights. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) has shown that human rights are inherent rights attached in every human being regardless of gender, age, status, race, nationality, or other differences. What is stated in the the UDHR above is a fundamental principle of human rights recognition. Such fundamental principles should be fully understood by all parties without exception. This is because everybody has the potential to violate human rights and vice versa even if the person is a prisoner or perpetrators of crime. The prisoners themselves are indeed people who have violated the human rights of others. However, it does not mean that they have lost their human rights forever and they can be treated inhumanely in order to redeem all his evil deeds.

4. Research Outcome and Analysis

Human rights are described as a universal moral issue. Some of these human rights are classified as interaliable (inevitable) and unviolable. Such human rights refer to as non derogable rights, namely human rights that cannot be denied or violated even if the state is in a state of "internal unrest", "civil war" or even "public emergency". These rights include : right to live, prohibition of torture; prohibition of slavery; prohibition of imprisonment solely for inability to fulfill a contractual obligation, prohibition of ex post facto, right to recognition as a person by the law, and freedom of religion.

Regarding to 1948's Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the most fundamental rights that cannot be separated from humans include : rights to livelihood and personal safety (article 3), prohibition of servitude, slavery and slave trade (article 4), prohibition of imposing torture and cruel treatment (article 5), right to legal recognition (article 6), right to equality before the law (article 7), right to get rehabilitation (article 8), prohibition of arbitrary arrest, detention or exile (article 9), right to a fair trial (article 10), presumption of innocence and prohibition on ex post facto law (article 11), right to have citizenship (article 16), right to have wealth (article 17), and freedom of thought, conscience and religion (article 18).

Prisoners' Rights Over Reintegrative Treatment

People whose physical freedom being taken away, namely prisoners on this note, must be treated humanely by respecting the dignity of the human rights attached in themselves. State Jail is run by "correctional system" as its fundamental guidance in treating prisoners.

Correctional system is a series of law enforcement that aims to make prisoners aware of their mistakes, improve themselves, and be unwilling to commit criminal acts so that they can be accepted again by the community, actively play a role in the form of national development, and live fairly as good and responsible citizens. Correctional measures can also be understood as an

embodiment of justice that aims to achieve social reintegration or the recovery of the unity of life, life and livelihoods between prisoners and the community. On that note, not only is social reintegration as a goal of coaching to be achieved, but social reintegration must also be placed as a fundamental right for prisoners to be fulfilled.

In order to achieve the goal of social reintegration, a number of coaching processes must be passed by a prisoner while in a prison, including personality coaching, education and spiritual development. Religious coaching of prisoner is intended to increase their faithful belief and devotion to God during the coaching period and after completing their punishment period. On the other hands, personality coaching in the intellectual field is needed so that the knowledge and mindset of the prisoners are increasing. This way, it can support positive activities needed during the coaching period.

As stipulated in article 14 paragraph (1) points a, b and c of Law Number 12 of 1995 concerning Correctional System, prisoners basic rights include performing worship according to their religion or belief, getting spiritual and physical care, getting education and teaching, obtaining health services and proper food, submitting complaints, obtaining reading material and follow broadcasts of other mass media that are not prohibited, getting wages or premiums for work done, receiving family visits, legal counsel, or other certain people, getting a reduction of punishment (remission), getting the opportunity to assimilate including leave to visit family, getting parole, getting leave before the end of punishment period, and obtaining other rights in accordance with the applicable laws and regulations. Even based on Government Regulation (PP) Number 31 of 1999 concerning Counseling and Guidance for Prisoners, religious education, skills and other coaching activities are given at the advanced coaching stage or started from the end of the admission/orientation stage to half (1/2) out of prisoners' punishment period.

Referring to article 42 of SMR, it is stated that as long as it can be carried out, every prisoner must be allowed to fulfill his religious needs individually or by attending religious activities in the institution and also have religious books in accordance with his religion and beliefs. The state must also be respectful when prisoners refuse visits by certain religion representatives.

There are two models in the criminal justice process that are presented by Herbert L. Packer in his book titled "*The Limits of the Criminal Sanction*" namely *Crime Control Model (CCM)* and *Due Process Model (DPM)*". In his view, the criminal justice process asserts itself into criminal law. Both of these processes have different ways of working, namely recognizing the importance of a written set of laws, but the focus is on different rules. The two models mentioned above have differences in the process of resolving criminal cases starting from the arrest process until the person is found guilty. The characteristic of the CCM focuses on the efficiency of how the judicial process works, which is quick capture and trial. On the other hands the characteristic of DPM focuses on how to protect the rights of suspects. On this note, a trial is a must in order to protect the suspects' rights. In fact, these two models greatly influence the criminal law in Indonesia, especially the characteristics of DPM that stand out with prisoners' rights protected.

As explained previously, the concept of the determination of prisoners' rights in the correctional law instrument should not be placed as complementary rights over prisoners' human rights in the correctional system.

5. Conclusion

This study concludes that the problems that occur in State Jail and Prison (Correctional Institution) are due to the unmet prisoners' basic rights. The state should be able to fulfill the

prisoners' rights even though these people are classified as 'lost' and having problem with the law. The state must exist to protect their rights. Prisoners' rights must be fulfilled. The state cannot make them worse or more evil.

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